

THERAPEUTIC ROLE OF *STHANIK CHIKITSA* IN *STREE ROGA*: AYURVEDIC PERSPECTIVES

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ABSTRACT

Women's health is a fundamental component of society's wellbeing. Due to an increasingly busy life and very competitive environment, many changes have occurred in the lifestyle of women that produce additional physical and emotional & mental stress on them. Because of this additional stress, women are more susceptible to environmental factors, and experience gynecological conditions such as leucorrhea, burning during micturition, dyspareunia and vaginal infections & foul smell, etc. According to Ayurveda, there are many local forms of therapies called *Sthanika Chikitsa* which are utilized in treating the various gynecological problems. *Sthanika Chikitsa* consists of various therapeutic procedures such as; *Yonidhavana*, *Yoni Pichu*, *Yoni Dhoopana*, *Yoni Varti*, *Yoni Lepana*, *Yoni Parisheka*, *Kshara Karma* and *Uttarbasti*, etc. Considering this fact present article discusses therapeutic role of *Sthanik Chikitsa* in various *Stree Roga*.

KEYWORDS: *Ayurveda*, *Stree Roga*, *Gynecological Disorders*, *Yoni Vyapad*, *Sthanika Chikitsa*.

INTRODUCTION

When a woman will get her menarche, she will occur many physical and physiological changes in her body. A woman must be aware of and manage these changes to stay healthy. Ayurveda focuses on the health of women and identifies numerous gynecological conditions (*Yonivyapada*). Ayurvedic local therapies known as *Sthanik Chikitsa* are of utmost importance in the disorders of *Tryavarta Yoni*, who appears to have gynecological disorders. *Sthanik Chikitsa* includes procedures such as *Yonidhawan*, *Yoni-Pichudharan*, *Yoni-Dhupan* and *Yoni-Varti*, etc. The benefits of *Sthanik Chikitsa* in gynecological disorders are depicted in **Figure 1**.^[1-3]

Figure 1: Benefits of *Sthanik Chikitsa*.

As mentioned above due to their antibacterial and antifungal qualities, these local treatments provide a variety of therapeutic advantages, including efficient cleaning and disinfection. Their tissue-repairing impact encourages endometrial healing and nourishing, while their anti-inflammatory action helps lessen redness,

swelling, and irritation. By reducing itching, burning, foul odor, and atypical discharges including white discharge and excessive flow, they significantly reduce symptoms. They also help systemic treatment by working in tandem with oral drugs. Many *Yonivyapad* problems, such as *Yonikandu*, *Yoni Strava*, *Yoni Paka*, *Upapluta* and *Yoni Karkashata* can be effectively managed with these remedies. By targeting localized pathology and boosting local immunity, these non-invasive local treatments are generally safe, economical, and produce excellent outcomes in common gynecological problems.^[4-7]

Yoni Dhawana

Ayurveda describes an important type of *Sthanik Chikitsa* called *Yoni Dhawana* that refers to the practice

of using water or a medicated decoction to clean infection. The cleaning process for *Yoni Dhawana* includes the use of a warm medicated liquid such as *Kwatha*, *Taila*, *Kshira paka* and *Siddha jala* to cleanse both the vagina and vaginal canal. *Yoni Dhawana* is generally applied between the 6th and 13th days of the menstruation cycle and lasts 1-1.5 minutes, with a potential for repeating three times a day for up to 8 days, depending on how severe the disease is at the time of application. The various decoctions (*Kwatha*) recommended for different types of *Yonivyapad* are mentioned in **Table 1**.

Table 1: Decoctions (*Kwatha*) recommended for different types of *Yonivyapad*.

Types of <i>Yonivyapad</i>	Recommended <i>Kwatha</i>	Main Therapeutic Action
<i>Yoni Srava</i>	<i>Triphala Kwatha</i>	Astringent, antimicrobial, reduces discharge, cleanses Yoni
<i>Yoni Paicchilya</i>	<i>Rajavrikshadi Kwatha</i>	<i>Lekhana</i> , <i>Kapha-shamana</i> , reduces sliminess
<i>Yoni Daurgandhya</i>	<i>Aragvadhadi Kwatha</i>	Deodorizing, antimicrobial, <i>Pittahara</i>
<i>Yoni Kandu</i>	<i>Guduchi-Triphala-Danti Kwatha</i>	<i>Kaphaghna</i> , <i>Kandughna</i> , anti-infective
<i>Artava Dushti – Vataja</i>	<i>Sarala-Mudgaparni Kwatha</i>	<i>Vata-shamana</i> , analgesic, improves <i>Artava</i> flow
<i>Artava Dushti – Pittaja</i>	<i>Gairika-Nimba Kwatha</i>	<i>Pittahara</i> , anti-inflammatory, <i>hemostatic</i>
<i>Artava Dushti – Kaphaja</i>	<i>Lodhra-Tinduka Kwatha</i>	Astringent, <i>Kapha-shamana</i> , regulates discharge

Yoni Pichu

The insertion of a medicated oil-soaked tampon (*Pichu*) into the vagina is referred to as *Yoni Pichu Dharana*. The *Pichu* is made out of a cotton swab, approximately 2 x 3 cm, which has been wrapped with sterile gauze and tied with a long length of thread for easy removal after it is soaked in the desired oil or liquid. Tampons made from oils are preferred, as they tend to stay in place and provide a longer period of effectiveness. *Yoni Pichu* is indicated in different types of conditions, including *Putraghni Yonivyapada*.^[5-8]

Yoni Dhoopan

In Ayurveda, the external genitalia are treated using a method known as *Yoni Dhoopan*. This method involves using therapeutic smoke as well as disinfectant to cleanse and heal *Bahya Yoni*. The therapy is typically performed for 3 to 5 minutes and depending upon the issue being treated, different combinations of herbs are recommended for fumigating the affected area as mentioned below.

- ✓ *Yoni Kandu* is best treated by putting out a mixture of *Haridra* and *Brihati*
- ✓ For *Shweta Pradara* the recommended blend of herbs includes *Sarala* and *Guggulu*
- ✓ The recommended combination for *Sutika Paricharya* is *Kushta* and *Guggulu* with *Ghrita*.

Yoni Lepana

Yoni Lepana refers to an external therapy using various herbal powders, which are all mixed together in a liquid to create a smooth paste of consistency. This paste

should apply directly on *Yonipradesha*. Depending on the consistency/thickness of the application, *Yoni Lepana* can be categorized into three groups; *Pralepa*, *Pradeha* and *Alepa*. The duration of a *Yoni Lepana* application typically lasts 3–4 hours, or until it becomes completely dry. Indications for *Yoni Lepana* include *Yoni Arsha* and *Vivrutta Yonivyapada*. Once applied, the *Lepa* should be removed immediately after drying.^[7-9]

Yoni Varti

Yoni Varti is prepared by combining finely ground medicinal drugs with appropriate binding or adhesive agents for inserting into the vagina. The average length of time that *Yoni Varti* should stay in the vagina before it is expelled is approximately two to three hours. *Yoni Varti* can be used to treat various types of gynecological problems, including; *Kaphaja Yonivyapada*, *Karnini Yonivyapada* and *Anartava*, etc.

Yoni Parisheka

Yoni Parisheka is an Ayurvedic procedure that involves soaking the vaginal area in hot water or using herbal oil. This treatment consists of pouring either hot water or herbal oil on the external part of the vagina. The purpose of this procedure is to reduce *Yoni shoola* and *Yoni shotha* caused by local inflammation in the vaginal area by increasing blood flow and circulation, alleviating tension, and pacifying excess *Doshas*.

Uttarbasti

Uttarbasti is an important para-surgical procedure considered best for *Vata dosha*. Insertion of medicated

oil decoction into *Uttarmarga* i.e., above or in front part of anus that is vagina or urethra is known as *Uttar Basti*. It is usually carried out under aseptic precaution, no need of any anaesthetic agent or analgesic during and after the procedure. *Uttarbasti* is indicated in *Yonirog, Vandhyatv, Yoni Vibhransha, Mutraghat, Mutrakruhha, Garbhashaya Rog, Asrugdar, Yonishula, Artava Vikar* and tubal block, etc.^[8-10]

Kshara Karma

Kshara are the substance that acts as a corrosive agent for any growth when used externally. *Kshara karma* is said to be superior to any other surgical or parasurgical measures due to its functions like *Chedana, Bhedana* and *Lekhana*. It can be applied in a narrowest place and internally where surgical procedures cannot be performed. It can be indicated for *Yoni Arsha*.^[9-12]

CONCLUSION

Sthanik Chikitsa is a very economical, safe and effective method of treatment with very few, if any, adverse effects. When *Sthanik Chikitsa* used correctly and applied according to aseptic techniques can become helpful for treating many *Stree Roga*. *Sthanik Chikitsa* includes *Yoni Dhawana, Yoni Pichu, Yoni Dhoopan, Yoni Lepana, Yoni Varti, Yoni Parisheka, Uttarbasti*, and *Kshara Karma*. In addition to promoting healing and relieving symptoms like discharge, discomfort, itching, inflammation, and infections, these local therapies work directly at the site of disease to cleanse, disinfect, and calm *Doshas*. These techniques are safe, economical, and very helpful when used carefully with the right indications and astringent aseptic precautions. They can be used as important adjuncts or primary therapies for a various *Yonivyapad*.

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